

10.5281/zenodo.7353506

Vol. 05 Issue 10 Oct - 2022

Manuscript ID: #0742

STUDY OF YOUTH PROBLEMS IN WEST KUTAI REGENCY

Fatimah Asyari, Amin Slamet, Maisyarah

Lecturer at the Faculty of Law, University of August 17, 1945, Samarinda

*Corresponding author: *Fatimah Asyari*

Email: asyarifatimah@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The aim of the research is to examine the problems faced by the Government in the context of empowering youth in the dimensions of social, national and state life in West Kutai Regency.

The research was conducted from August to October 2021 in West Kutai Regency. East Kalimantan Province.

This study uses legal research methods, namely by conducting Normative Juridical and Empirical Juridical legal research. The stages of research activities are: (1) identification of the problems faced in youth development in West Kutai Regency; (2) inventory of legal materials needed related to Youth, systemization and analysis of legal materials; (3) observation and data collection; (4) data analysis; and (5) reporting.

The results of the study show that (1) the problems or obstacles faced by the Government of West Kutai Regency in the context of empowering youth in the dimensions of social, national and state life in West Kutai Regency include: (a) there are no facilities and infrastructure such as youth arenas in West Kutai Regency ; (b) Lack of youth activities in West Kutai Regency; (c) youth organizations/youth communities and the like, have never reported their activities to the West Kutai Regency Government cq the West Kutai Regency Youth and Sports Office, this has become one of the reasons for the lack of communication to jointly develop West Kutai Regency through youth activities; and (d) lack of information related to youth activities in West Kutai Regency; and (2) the efforts made by the Government of West Kutai Regency in the field of youth development, namely by carrying out youth awareness, empowerment and development activities.

KEY WORDS:

Youth Problems, West Kutai.

This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 License.

INTRODUCTION

Indonesia has the fourth largest population in the world, based on Population Administration data as of June 2021 the total population of Indonesia is 272,229,372 people, consisting of 137,521,557 people are men and 134,707,815 people are women. Quoted from the results of the 2020 population census, Indonesia's population is dominated by young people or generation Z, namely residents born in the period 1997-2021 or aged 8 to 23 years. The number of generation Z in Indonesia reaches 75.49 million people or the equivalent with 27.94 percent of the total population in Indonesia. Furthermore, the second most dominant population comes from the millennial generation, namely those born in the period 1981-1996 or aged between 24 to 39 years, which totaled 69.38 million people or 25.87 percent of the total population of Indonesia (BPS, 2021).

The term 'youth' is not an empty marker, youth is a floating signifier whose meaning is influenced by socio-political processes and temporary cultural practices. Thus 'youth' is a marker of life with its meaning which can be fixed or changing [1]. On the shoulders of youth there are various expectations, especially from other generations. This is because they are expected to become the next generation, who will continue the struggle of the previous generation, and the generation that must continue the relay of development. Youth has a very strategic role in shaping the character and personality of the nation as one of the efforts to build Indonesian people as a whole, who are self-identified, independent and productive so that basic human needs are fulfilled, which will continue to exist and develop according to the stages or cycles of human life.

Youth has a very strategic function and role so that it needs to develop its potential and role through awareness, empowerment and development as part of national development. So to realize the goals of national development, youth who are noble, healthy, tough, intelligent, independent and professional are needed. Awareness, empowerment and development of youth development, youth services are needed in the dimension of development in all areas of social, national and state life as stipulated in Law Number 40 of 2009 concerning Youth which is based on Pancasila and the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia.

As one of the basic human needs, ideally youth empowerment should be accessible and easily accessible, this is in line with the concept of a welfare state. Where the dimension is the government's obligation to strive for general welfare (*bestuurszorg*) which is one of the characteristics of the welfare state concept.

According to E. Utrecht, the existence of this *bestuurszorg* is a sign indicating the existence of a "welfare state". BagirManan stated that the socio-economic dimension of a state based on law is in the form of the obligation of the state or government to realize and guarantee social welfare (general welfare) in an atmosphere of maximum prosperity according to the principle of social justice for all people [2]. The Indonesian government is a government in the dimension of a welfare state because the government's duties are not solely in the field of administration, but must also carry out social welfare in order to achieve state goals, which are carried out through national development [3].

However, if studied in depth, not all young people have lofty ideals to make this nation a more advanced nation. There are still many young people in this nation who do not live up to the expectations of previous generations. We can see that many young people today are actually doing things that should not be done by a generation that is the nation's hope. Even today, many young people are destroying their own future. Several issues provide evidence that the current generation of youth is acting against existing norms,

West Kutai Regency has an obligation to raise awareness, empower and develop as stipulated in Law Number 40 of 2009 concerning Youth. This obligation is the capital of the nation-building process, youth as a moral force, social control and agent of change as an embodiment of its strategic function, role, characteristics and position in national development. For this reason, the responsibilities and strategic roles of youth in all dimensions of development need to be increased within the national legal framework in accordance with the values contained in Pancasila and the mandate of the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia with the principles of Belief in One Almighty God, humanity, nationality, diversity, democracy, justice, participation, togetherness, equality and independence.

The aim of the research is to examine the problems faced by the Government in the context of empowering youth in the dimensions of social, national and state life in West Kutai Regency.

THEORETICAL STUDY AND EMPIRICAL PRACTICE

A. Theoretical Studies

1. Definition of “Pemuda”/Youth

- a. Law Number 40 of 2009 concerning Youth (State Gazette of the Republic of Indonesia Number 148, Supplement to the State Gazette of the Republic of Indonesia Number 5238) provides a definition of youth as Indonesian citizens entering an important period of growth and development aged 16-30 years.
- b. The United Nations definition of “youth” includes those aged 15 – 24 years, overlapping with the age of “children” which includes ages 0 – 17 years. According to WHO it is classified as young people aged 10-24 years, while youth or adolescence is in the 10-19 year group [4].
- c. Youth is a generation whose shoulders are burdened with various expectations, especially from other generations. This understanding arose because the group's youth were prepared to become successors, fillers and who would carry out the implementation of sustainable development [5].

2. Definition of “Kepemudaan”/Youth

Youth development is carried out through a process in all matters relating to youth services, which development focuses on the process of awareness, empowerment and youth development.

Youth development is carried out in order to improve the spirit of leadership, entrepreneurship and youth pioneering so that in turn it can produce advanced youth, namely youth with character, capacity and competitiveness.

Youth is defined as citizens who are entering an important period of growth and development aged 16 (sixteen) to 30 (thirty) years. The increase in the number of youth activities is expected to be able to bring progress in the youth sector so that the role and participation of youth in various development fields is increasing.

Youth can be interpreted in the form of various things related to the potential, responsibilities, rights, character, capacity, self-actualization, and aspirations of youth [6]

According to [5] that the essence of youth is viewed from two assumptions: (1) The appreciation of the process of human development is not as a continuous continuum but fragmentary, fragmented and each fragment has its own meaning, youth is distinguished from children and parents and each of those fragments represents its own value; and (2) In addition to the assumption of life insight is the position of youth in the direction of life itself. Youth as a subject in life, of course, has its own value in supporting and driving life together. This can only happen if the behavior of the youth itself is viewed as an interaction in the environment in a broad sense.

3. Youth Awareness, Empowerment and Development

a. Youth Awareness

Youth awareness is an activity aimed at understanding and responding to environmental changes. Awareness is essentially the development of the character of Indonesian youth including faith and piety, noble character, national insight, leadership, responsibility, identity, independence and high nationalism.

Youth awareness in the form of movements in ideological, political, legal, economic, socio-cultural, defense and security aspects in understanding and responding to changes in the strategic environment, both domestic and global as well as preventing and managing risks. In youth awareness, the Ministry of Youth and Sports has carried out various programs and activities, namely facilitating an increase in nationalism, peace and environmental insight, as well as facilitating the improvement of scouting education.

b. Youth Empowerment

Youth empowerment is an activity to awaken the potential and active role of youth. Young people are expected to be empowered and capable with all their potential. The talents and talents of young people in various fields of art, science and technology, and others are relatively large, so it is hoped that the government can facilitate these potentials so that they can develop better, so that young people can empower themselves based on this potential.

Youth empowerment should be carried out in a planned, systematic and sustainable manner to increase the potential and quality of physical, mental, spiritual, self-knowledge and organizational skills towards youth independence. Youth empowerment is carried out by involving the participation of the community, business world and other youth stakeholders.

In empowering youth, the Ministry of Youth and Sports has implemented various programs including; (1) facilitating capacity building in the fields of science and technology, faith and piety, arts and culture; and (2) facilitating the empowerment of youth organizations.

c. Youth Development

Youth development as stipulated in Law Number 40 of 2009 concerning Youth, focuses on 3 (three) things, namely: (1) youth leadership development, namely activities to develop exemplary potential, influence, and youth mobilization; (2) youth entrepreneurship development, namely activities to develop potential skills and business independence, and (3) youth pioneering development, namely activities to develop potential in pioneering roads, making breakthroughs, responding to challenges, and providing solutions to various problems. Leadership Development that has been carried out by the Ministry of Youth and Sports, including: facilitation of National Youth and Sports Resilience training, facilitation of youth leadership training; facilitation of Undergraduate Youth Driving Development in Rural Areas; and facilitation of youth entrepreneurship training [7]

B. Empirical Practice

Considering the very important role of youth in development and as the nation's next generation, youth development must be carried out in a planned, directed and integrated manner.

RESEARCH METHODS

A. Time and Place

The research was conducted from August to October 2021 in West Kutai Regency. East Kalimantan Province.

B. Approach Method

This study uses legal research methods, namely by conducting Normative Juridical and Empirical Juridical legal research. It is stated as normative because this research starts from existing regulations as legal norms, while it is empirical because it is carried out by conducting interviews and research or direct review of the reality that occurs [8].

The stages of the research carried out were: (1) identification of the problems faced in youth development in West Kutai Regency; (2) inventory of legal materials needed related to Youth, systemization and analysis of legal materials; (3) observation and data collection; (4) data analysis; and (5) reporting.

C. Data Collection and Analysis

Data collection was carried out through literature study or literature review, observation, situational analysis, interviews and discussions. Interviews were conducted with government officials, community leaders, representatives of youth organizations and communities related to research activities. Data analysis was carried out in a qualitative descriptive manner.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Overview of the Region

West Kutai Regency is one of 10 regencies/cities in East Kalimantan Province. West Kutai Regency with the capital city of Sendawar, the result of division of the Kutai Regency area which has been established based on Law Number 47 of 1999 concerning the formation of Nunukan Regency, Malinau Regency, West Kutai Regency, East Kutai Regency and Bontang City dated October 4, 1999. Symbolically inaugurated by Minister of Home Affairs R.I. on October 12, 2009 in Jakarta and operationally inaugurated by the Governor of East Kalimantan on November 5, 1999 in Sendawar. The area of West Kutai Regency is 20,381.59 km² or approximately 15.79% of the total area of East Kalimantan Province.

Administratively, the boundaries of West Kutai Regency to the north are Mahakam Hulu Regency, east to Kutai Kartanegara Regency, south to North Penajam Paser Regency and to the west are Central Kalimantan Province.

Before the expansion, the number of sub-districts in West Kutai Regency was 21 sub-districts consisting of 236 villages and 4 sub-districts. However, after the issuance of Law no. 2 of 2013 concerning the Establishment of Mahakam Ulu Regency in East Kalimantan Province, 5 sub-Districts namely Long Apari, Long Pahangai, Long Bagun, Laham and Long Hubung officially became the territory of Mahakam Ulu Regency, so that the number of Districts in West Kutai Regency was reduced to 16 sub-Districts.

B. State of Youth in West Kutai Regency

According to data from the West Kutai Regency Youth and Sports Service for 2021, the state of youth organizations in West Kutai Regency is that there are 60 organizations. However, there are no youth organizations that are active and report on the activities that have been carried out. Youth organizations in West Kutai Regency according to sub-district domiciles and areas of organizational activity are as follows:

- Melaksub-District consists of: (a) OKP AnakSorga Front - Religion, (b) Muhammadiyah Youth OKP - Religion; (c) OKP Youth Mahakam Kutai Barat – Social Society and others; and (d) MacanDahan Scooter Club (MADASC) – Community, Social, Hobby Distribution and others.
- MookManaarBulatin sub-District, namely the Rempah Jaya KarangTaruna (RMP) - Badminton, Taekwondo, Knowledge Education and others.
- SekolaqDarat sub-District consists of: (a) TonaarHarapan Youth Organization – Sports, youth; (b) Rimba Lestari Youth Organization, Sports, Tourism, Arts; (c) KarangTarunaLeleng – youth, sports, tourism, arts; (d) Mulawarman Youth Organization – youth, sports, tourism, arts; (e) Tunas Harapan Youth Organization - Youth, Sports, Tourism, Arts; (f) KarangTaruna " TarunaMulia " - youth, sports, tourism, arts; (g) KarangTarunaMandiri - youth, sports, tourism, arts; and (h) Tunas Muda Youth Organization - Youth, Sports, Tourism, Arts.
- LinggangBigung sub-District consists of: (a) KarangTarunaKerai Jaya – Sports; (b) KarangTaruna Tunas Muda – Sports, Arts and Sinoman (Karya Bhakti); (c) Mincei Jaya Youth Organization – Sports and Arts; (d) KarangTaruna Tunas Jaya – Sports and arts; (e) KarangTarunaJanturPermai – Youth and Sports; (f) Catholic Youth (OMK) - Social Religion; (g) Aco Putra Youth Organization – Sports; (h) Tunas Boys Youth Organization – Sports and Social Affairs; (i) Bukit Pesona Youth Organization – Sports; (j) LulungPermai Youth Organization – Sports; (k) KarangTaruna Tunas Karya – Sports and Arts; (l) OKP Kelapeh – Handicrafts, Tourism and Nature Conservation; (m) OKP TeliatnHemaq – Forestry, Nature Conservation and Tourism; (n) KPA MDDL – Environment, Nature Conservation and Tourism; and (o) PersikMandiri Youth Organization – Sports.
- Teringsub-District consists of: (a) KarangTaruna Tunas Harapan; (b) Banjarejo Youth Organization; (c) LinggangMuaraMujan Youth Organization; (d) MuyubUlu Youth Organization; (e) KelianDalam Youth Organization; (f) KarangTaruna Margo Mulio – Religion, Sports and Arts; and (g) Community Service - Social.
- Long Iramsub-District consists of: (a) KarangTaruna - Football, Volleyball, Badminton, Social and others and (b) Nature Lovers Youth Association (IPPA) - Environment.
- MuaraLawasub-District consists of: (a) KarangTarunaBatuqBura – Sports and Social Affairs; (b) Lotaq Youth Organization – Sports and Social Affairs; (c) Tementang Jaya Youth Organization – Sports and Social

- Affairs; (d) PayangMendiri Youth Organization – Sports and Social Affairs; (e) TakaqRamaq Youth Organization – Sports and Social Affairs; (f) MuaraLawa Village Youth Organization – Sports and Social Affairs; (g) KarangTaruna Lestari Pangan Jaya – Sports, Arts, Agriculture and Social Affairs; and (h) Youth Troops Youth Association of England – Sports, Arts and Social Affairs.
8. MuaraPahusub-District consists of: (a) United Millennial Youth Organization – Sports; (b) Tunas Mekar Youth Organization – Sports and Social; (c) Sebelang Village Youth Organization; (d) KarangTarunaKampungTanjungLaong; and (e) Menthex Youth Organization – Sports and Social.
 9. Penyinggahansub-District consists of: (a) Prosperous Youth Organization - Football, Futsal, Volleyball, Tingkilan and Jepen Arts; (b) KarangTarunaHarapan Jaya – Football, Futsal, Badminton, Volleyball, Spirituality and Modern Art; (c) BinaSendawar Youth Organization – Football and Badminton; (d) KarangTaruna Budi Sanjaya – Football, Futsal, Badminton, Volly ball and arts; (e) KarangTarunaBahari – Football, Badminton and Volleyball; and (f) Erlangga Youth Organization – Football, Badminton and Volleyball.
 10. Jempangsub-District consists of: (a) Youth Organization Grosingo – Sports and Social Affairs; and (b) PB Telauur – Badminton Sport.
 11. Bongansub-District, namely KarangTarunaResak Village – Sports, Arts and Social Affairs.
 12. SiluqNguraisub-District, namely the KakatnMaju Youth Organization – Sports and Social Affairs.

C. Study of Youth in West Kutai Regency Conditions and Problems Faced

The results of the study show that the obstacles faced in youth development in West Kutai Regency include:

1. There are no facilities and infrastructure such as a youth arena in West Kutai Regency.

The government of West Kutai district should have at least built 1 (one) youth arena, which will later become a place for channeling youth creative activities.

2. Lack of youth activities in West Kutai Regency.

We recommend that the West Kutai Regency Government through the Youth and Sports Service, West Kutai Regency KNPI and youth organizations and communities should increase communication and collaboration to create an annual youth event, such as a youth creative week.

3. Youth organizations/youth communities and the like, have never reported their activities to the West Kutai Regency Government or the West Kutai Regency Youth and Sports Office, this has become one of the causes of the lack of communication to jointly develop West Kutai Regency through youth activities.

The Youth and Sports Office of West Kutai Regency should be more active in conducting socialization regarding the development of youth organizations/communities and the like from the village, sub-district to district levels.

4. Lack of information related to youth activities in West Kutai Regency.

It is recommended that the West Kutai Regency Youth and Sports Service must have special social media related to youth, such as websites, Instagram, Facebook and youth service numbers. The social media must contain updated information related to youth activities, such as youth events, competitions that can motivate achievements and so on.

5. Other important matters that require regulation in West Kutai Regency

Another important matter is related to the recommendation for the formation of youth organizations/communities and the like by registering and inputting data online which can be accessed by all people of West Kutai Regency, with socialization first.

The results of the study are almost in accordance with the results of research reported by [9], namely several things that have caused delays in youth development in North Luwu Regency, including: (1) the decline in the spirit of idealism, patriotism, and nationalism among the community, including the spirit of youth; (2) the uncertainty experienced by the younger generation about their future; (3) the unbalanced number of young people with educational facilities (formal and non-formal) available; (4) lack of field and job opportunities among youth; (5) the high unemployment rate among the younger generation; (6) the high number of underage marriages; (7) the high rate of promiscuity among the younger generation, thus endangering the nation's moral

foundations; (8) the high use of drugs among the younger generation; (9) the absence of laws and regulations concerning the younger generation; and (10) lack of guidance on youth character.

D. Youth Development Strategy and Policy in West Kutai Regency

In connection with youth problems in West Kutai Regency, several strategies and policies need to be implemented to overcome them, namely: (1) conducting socialization to increase public awareness of the problems faced by youth; (2) encouraging and supporting the implementation of positive youth activities; (3) provide greater access to education for youth who wish to continue their education; (4) encouraging youth activities in the religious field; and (5) encouraging cooperation between the Regional Government and local youth organizations. Furthermore, the development of youth organizations can be carried out in various ways, ranging from financial assistance to the provision of facilities and infrastructure that support the activities of youth organizations.

Youth development that has been carried out in West Kutai Regency, namely as follows: (1) awareness efforts through State Defense training for Youth in 2019, the Youth Movement Concerning the Beautiful Environment in 2019 sd. 2020, and selection and sending of JPD & JPI participants from 2016 to 2021; (2) efforts to empower through socialization about the dangers of drug use in 2017 to 2019, fostering faith and piety of Youth at the East Kalimantan Province Dispora in 2021; and (3) development efforts through entrepreneurship training activities for youth, and facilitation of young entrepreneurs in the promotion of development. While development activities in the field of leadership and pioneering have never been implemented.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

A. Conclusion

Based on the results of the study it can be concluded, namely as follows:

1. The problems or obstacles faced by the Government of West Kutai Regency in the context of empowering youth in the dimensions of social, national and state life in West Kutai Regency include: (a) there are no facilities and infrastructure such as youth arenas in West Kutai Regency; (b) Lack of youth activities in West Kutai Regency; (c) youth organizations/youth communities and the like, have never reported their activities to the West Kutai Regency Government cq the West Kutai Regency Youth and Sports Office, this has become one of the reasons for the lack of communication to jointly develop West Kutai Regency through youth activities; and (d) lack of information related to youth activities in West Kutai Regency.
2. Efforts made by the Government of West Kutai Regency in the field of youth development, namely by carrying out activities in the form of awareness, empowerment and youth development.

B. Suggestion

1. To overcome youth problems in West Kutai Regency, collaboration and coordination between the government, the community, youth organizations and related parties are needed.
2. It is necessary to make a Regulation on Youth in the form of a regional regulation which clearly regulates the roles, rights and obligations of each related party, both individually and institutionally and/or institutions.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- [1] Hilmar Farid. 2011. In “Rebellion and Rebellion: Youth in Indonesian Literature”, (Prisma, Vol. 30, 2011)
- [2] BagirManan. 1999. Thoughts of the Indonesian Constitutional State, Paper at the National Scientific Meeting of the Faculty of Law, University of Padjadjaran, Bandung, 6 April 1999..
- [3] SjachranBasah. 1985. Existence and Benchmarks of Administrative Courts in Indonesia, Alumni, Bandung.
- [4] DindinSupratman. 2018. The Prevalence Of Youth And National Security Narcotics And Threats Lost Generation, JurnalLitbangSukowati I. Volume 1 Number 2 Year 2018, page. 121.
- [5] Taufik Abdullah. 2018. Youth And Social Change, LP3S Jakarta.
- [6] Article 1 paragraph (2) Law Number 40 of 2009 concerning Youth (State Gazette of the Republic of Indonesia of 2009 Number 148, Supplement to the State Gazette of the Republic of Indonesia Number 5238).
- [7] Ministry of Youth and Sports, Ministry of Youth and Sports Strategic Plan 2016-2019, Ministry of Youth and Sports, 2017. Hlm. 8-10
- [8] Marzuki, P.M. 2008. Legal Research, Kencana, Jakarta,
- [9] Sudirman, I., M. Aminawar; A.S. Alam; , I.K. Sakharina; M. Darwis; M.E. Kurniawan. 2018. Study of Youth Development Policy Strategies in North Luwu Regency. BangdaSimpurusiang Journal 1 (1): 61 – 79

LEGISLATION

The 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia.

Law Number 40 of 2009 concerning Youth (State Gazette of the Republic of Indonesia of 2009 Number 148, Supplement to the State Gazette of the Republic of Indonesia Number 5238).

Regulation of the Minister of Youth and Sports of the Republic of Indonesia Number 0059 of 2013 concerning Youth Leadership Development.

Regulation of the Minister of Youth and Sports of the Republic of Indonesia Number 0945 of 2015 concerning the Functions and Duties of Executing Youth Entrepreneurial Capital Institutions.